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The Economic Situation of Families in the Italian Regions in the Period 2016-2022

It has worsened significantly during the post covid 19

Istat calculates the value of the economic situation of families in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the number of families who declare that their economic situation has worsened or much worsened compared to the previous year. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2016 and 2022.

Ranking of the regions by value of the economic situation of families in the Italian regions in 2022. Piedmont is in first place by value of the economic situation of the family with a value of 40.3, followed by the Marche with a value of 39.8 units and from Abruzzo with a value of 38.7 units. In the middle of the table are Umbria with a value of 35.7 units, followed by Molise with a value of 35.6 units and Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of 35.5 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of 30.4 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 29.2 units and Campania with a value of 28.6 units.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in the economic situation of families between 2016 and 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place in terms of value of the economic situation of families between 2016 and 2022 with a value of 50.5% with a variation from an amount of 20.2 units up to a value of 30.4 units or equal to an amount of 10.2 units. Tuscany follows with a variation equal to an amount of 22.65% corresponding to a growth from 30.9 units up to 37.9 units or equal to an amount of 7 units. In third place is Emilia Romagna with a variation of 21.64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 30.5 units up to 37.1 units. In the middle of the table are Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to an amount of 1.72% corresponding to a variation from 34.9 units up to 35.5 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to an amount of 0.3% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 33.8 units up to 33.9 units. In eleventh place is Puglia with a variation of 0.00%. Calabria closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -17.53% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 40.5 units up to a value of 33.4 units, followed by Basilicata with a variation equal to an amount of -20.65% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 36.8 units down to 29.2 units. Campania closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -23.53% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 37.4 units up to a value of 28.6 units. On average, the value of the economic situation of families increased from an amount of 34.9 units up to a value of 35.2 units or a growth of 0.84%.

Ranking of the Italian macro-regions between 2016 and 2022. The economic situation of families has had a fluctuating trend in the Italian macro-regions. There are some Italian macro-regions in which the value of the economic situation of families has increased, i.e. the regions of the Centre-North, and regions in which the economic situation of families has decreased, i.e. the southern regions. In

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particular, the economic situation of families worsened in the North where between 2016 and 2022 the value increased by 9.48%, in the North-West with +8.64%, in the North-East with +10.88% , in the Center with +3.58%. The value of the family's economic situation decreased in the following regions: Southern Italy with -11.14%, Southern Italy with -12.05%, Islands with -10.02%. We can note two orientations for all the Italian macro-regions analyzed. A pre-covid period in which the value of the economic situation of families decreased in all Italian macro-regions. And then a post-Covid 19 period in which the value of the family's economic situation increased significantly.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The optimal value of k would be equal to 2. However, in the case of k=2 a situation occurs in which there are two clusters, one with 19 regions and the other with a single region. However, I chose k=3 as it has a greater capacity to represent the heterogeneity of the Italian regions. Three clusters are thus identified:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, Marche, Valle d'Aosta, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Tuscany, Abruzzo, Lazio, Piedmont, Basilicata, Veneto, Molise, Campania;
- Cluster 2: Trentino Alto Adige;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Sardinia, Calabria, Umbria.

Considering the average value of the clusters we can note the presence of the following clusters: $C3 > C1 > C2$. It follows that the condition of families tends to be high in some regions of southern Italy, namely Sicily, Sardinia and Calabria and in Umbria. However, the majority of Italian regions are found in Cluster 1. Cluster 1 is very heterogeneous and is made up of both southern regions, regions of Central Italy and northern regions. Finally, Cluster 2 is made up of a single region, namely Trentino Alto Adige, with lower levels of economic conditions of families compared to other Italian regions.

Conclusions. The value of the economic condition of families grew on average in the Italian regions between 2016 and 2022. However, we can note two phases in the trend of the analyzed variable. A first pre-Covid 19 phase in which there was a generalized reduction in the value of the economic condition of families, and a post-covid 19 phase in which the value of the economic condition of families began to grow in the Italian regions. However, the value of the economic situation of families has grown significantly in the Central-Northern regions compared to the southern regions. This element highlights the fact that Covid 19 has had a much more significant economic impact in the regions of Central-North compared to the regions of Southern Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	32,7	29,9	26,8	24,3	29	29,4	35,8	3,10	9,48
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	32,4	30,4	27,3	24,1	29,5	29,3	35,2	2,80	8,64
<i>Nord-est</i>	33,1	29,1	26,1	24,7	28,1	29,6	36,7	3,60	10,88
<i>Centro</i>	33,5	30,3	28,6	27,4	30,8	32,4	34,7	1,20	3,58
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	38,6	36,7	31,1	26,8	28	31,1	34,3	-4,30	-11,14
<i>Sud</i>	36,5	33,8	28,9	25,3	27,5	30,3	32,1	-4,40	-12,05
<i>Isole</i>	42,9	42,3	35,4	29,8	29	32,7	38,6	-4,30	-10,02

Regione	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	35,1	33,2	29,3	27,6	31,7	30,8	40,3
Valle d'Aosta	32,5	29,4	26,2	25,6	25,5	33,1	34,8
Liguria	33,8	33,3	27,6	25	29,2	27,8	33,9
Lombardia	31	28,7	26,4	22,4	28,7	28,8	33,1
Trentino-Alto Adige	20,2	16,5	16,4	15,7	21,3	26,1	30,4
Veneto	38,1	32,2	28,2	28,8	30	30,7	38
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	34,9	33,2	27,5	23,6	29,5	30,7	35,5
Emilia-Romagna	30,5	27,5	25,6	22,8	27,3	28,8	37,1
Toscana	30,9	29,2	25,6	26,2	32,1	35	37,9
Umbria	40,4	36,3	30,9	30,3	24,8	28,9	35,7
Marche	34,1	32	26,2	24,4	26,6	31,3	39,8
Lazio	34	29,7	30,8	28,6	31,9	31,5	31,4

Abruzzo	33,8	32,9	28,3	27,5	27,2	30,5	38,7
Molise	36,8	32	31,9	25,1	27,1	26,8	35,6
Campania	37,4	34,9	29,7	23,5	28,4	30,6	28,6
Puglia	34,2	31,6	28,1	25,8	28,7	30,8	34,2
Basilicata	36,8	25,9	26,7	23,4	21,2	26,4	29,2
Calabria	40,5	38,9	29,1	28,1	24,9	30,2	33,4
Sicilia	43,9	43,5	35	30,3	29,8	33,1	38,7
Sardegna	39,9	38,9	36,7	28,4	26,8	31,7	38,4